

SHORT NOTES

Complexes of Lower Valent Rhenium

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The analogy of bivalent and trivalent rhenium with the corresponding iron compounds has been brought about in earlier communications¹⁻². It has been observed that in certain of its compounds rhenium also resembles ruthenium.

The nitroso compounds of ruthenium³ are well known for their exceptional stability. Analogous rhenium compound of the type ReNOCl_3 has been prepared by heating silver hexachlororhenate(IV) in an atmosphere of pure nitric oxide. The chemical analysis of the finally isolated compound indicates the composition to be $\text{ReNOCl}_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The oxidation number of the group $[\text{ReNO}]$ has been proved to be 3. The nitrosochloride is a hygroscopic substance, soluble in organic solvents like alcohols, acetone, etc. and also in water, but the aqueous solution is not stable. The nitroso group is firmly attached to the metal and is not easily knocked off in acid medium. In alkaline medium this is, however, converted to nitrite and the compound decomposes. An ethanolic solution of the compound shows an absorption maximum at 450 m μ .

Starting from a solution of ReNOCl_3 and KCl in HCl (conc.), needle-shaped crystalline compound, presumably of composition $\text{K}_2[\text{ReNOCl}_3]$, has been prepared. ReNOCl_3 easily takes up pyridine and other ligands. The characterisation of these compounds is in progress, details of which will be published later.

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2. *Idem*, this *Journal*, 1963, **40**, 707, 709, 813, 815.
3. Joly, *Compt. rend.*, 1888, **107**, 994; Claus, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1860, **79**, 35.
4. Werner, *Ber.*, 1907, **40**, 2014; Charonnat, *Ann. chim.*, 1931, **16**, 227.